

THE ROLE OF SPORTS IN THE SYSTEM OF GENERAL PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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ELSEVIER

Allaxanov Azamat

*Assistant, Nukus state pedagogical institute,
Nukus, Uzbekistan*

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Abstract: The article analyzes the main approaches to the use of sports games in the school physical education system. The most important purpose of sports in secondary school is to acquaint students with the types of sports games and exercises, to lay the foundation for the right technique..

Keywords: sports games, physical culture, physical development, physical culture and sports activities, school physical education system

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Recently, with the physical education and sports of the younger generation is becoming increasingly clear that the traditional and long-established forms of practice no longer meet modern requirements and need to be transformed into more effective forms. Hence the innovative pedagogical There is a need to look for new ideas and approaches to the organization of physical culture and sports using technology [1].

The most effective way to increase movement efficiency is physical activity. The content of physical education is material, aesthetic and spiritual represented by a set of values. The result of physical education is physical fitness and skills, the level of perfection of abilities, a high level of development of vital forces, sports achievements, moral, aesthetic, intellectual development, orientation to a healthy lifestyle.

The main goals and objectives of physical culture and sports in secondary schools today are to increase physical culture among students, to form a preparation for a healthy lifestyle, to develop interest in sports, to exercise regularly, to develop moral, emotional, focuses on the formation and development of intellectual, socio-cultural and aesthetic personality, creative abilities and cognitive needs [2]. Admittedly, it's a competition for high school students processes such as fierce competition among participants, the promotion of only a small group of winners, and the traditional model of organizing sports competitions have serious shortcomings. This is to show the participants the feeling of victory in any way and way, to show their superiority over others, to achieve

fame, to gain material benefits associated with victory, creates a desire to win valuable prizes (even if it is harmful to health and violates ethical principles).

In the education system, educators often use four main areas of physical education and sports [3]. The first direction is primarily aimed at the acquisition of certain knowledge by students in the field of physical education and sports, as well as the development of skills and abilities. The second area focuses on the high level of development of physical qualities and the effectiveness of training by increasing the number of mandatory exercises. The third area is sports-oriented, first and foremost based on the rational combination of departmental and classroom forms of training, the implementation of certain sports. The main task in this process is to develop systematic training skills for the preferred types of physical activity.

In the fourth area, the health of students and their level of physical development, physical fitness is considered the highest value of a person [4]. All four areas of physical education in the school will be ensured through the implementation of each of them, with a strong emphasis on the creation of flexible curricula, taking into account the needs and interests of students [5]. She is also a teacher Given the possibilities, it is assumed that it should consist of two blocks: mandatory (basic) and differential (variable) [6, 7]. Alternative forms of improving physical education, physical education In contrast to the traditional forms of the lesson, it allows to organize classes in study groups in the form of extracurricular activities. At the same time, students are free to choose the type of course based on their interests and aspirations have freedom [8, 9].

Sports is a historically developed social phenomenon, an independent type of human sports [10, 11]. It can be a means of play, self-improvement, self-knowledge, sports, recreation, general physical development, or social education. Sports games used for physical development are different, but they can still be divided into sports and physical activity. Sport games are the highest level of action games. However, sports games differ from mobile games by unique rules, duration of the game, a certain composition of participants, the size and layout of the fields, equipment and inventory, etc., which allows for quality competitions will give [12, 13, 14,].

Sports competitions require more physical strength and willpower from participants. In sports, two very important factors are objectively combined: on the one hand, children gain aesthetic and moral satisfaction from this competition, expand their knowledge base about the environment, and on the other hand, they participate in practical activities. It's all about personality contributes to the formation of [15, 16].

Thus, sports games are one of the most effective and effective educational tools for comprehensive physical training, improving the character traits and functions of the game organization. Sports games effectively affect the

psychological and pedagogical learning processes of schoolchildren: develop skills such as thinking, attention, memory, perception, imagination, reading, and physiologically improve the respiratory system, metabolism, blood circulation . Students work with teachers to seek out and introduce innovative pedagogical technologies to organize learning activities, and in this process, the attractiveness and importance of play activities for school students becomes apparent. Sports games teacher to students allows them to solve a number of important and strategic tasks in working with, satisfying their interests and needs for physical activity, learning to control their own body, stabilizing their emotions, not only physical, but also mental, psychophysiological, creative abilities , display moral qualities makes Regular use of sports games in physical education classes, extended breaks in schools, and long day groups can help optimize motor regimen and improve health and mental performance. Sports games can rightly be called a means of harmonious development and physical fitness of students.

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